

The Datasets

Microbes Ideation Workshop Report

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Vancouver, Canada

May 2-3, 2024

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Introduction

This report summarizes the outcomes of the Microbes Ideation Workshop, hosted by Align to Innovate on May 2 and 3, 2024 in Vancouver, Canada. The workshop brought together scientists and technologists to identify key microbiology dataset ideas that will enable the next generation of predictive models.

Throughout the workshop, participants engaged in a series of guided sessions designed to explore current challenges in microbial datasets and identify promising projects to address some of these issues. The overarching goal was to distill these ideas into well-defined dataset draft proposals, each accompanied by potential approaches to data (and metadata) collection and use for model creation.

The preliminary dataset ideas, predictive models, and data collection methods developed during the workshop are detailed herein and will be utilized by Align to Innovate's Open Datasets Initiative as foundational elements guiding our next public data collection efforts.

Background

Align to Innovate is a nonprofit organization that aims to cultivate an ecosystem of reproducible, scalable, and shareable life science research enabled by automation. We work to coordinate the expertise and needs of researchers to identify and execute large, collaborative, data-intensive projects. We accelerate these projects by creating venues for agenda setting, facilitating partnerships, and removing technical bottlenecks from the ecosystem. Through these efforts, we aim to move the field of biology toward a new paradigm of automation-first research.

Our Open Datasets Initiative is accelerating the use of automated labs and pioneering robust, data collection methods with the goal of collecting and sharing high-quality, AI-ready biological datasets. Our datasets are a **collaborative, community effort** and represent a new paradigm for whole-field collaboration to address important problems in life science. We work with experts in biology, machine learning, and automation to identify the most important “missing” life science datasets and to create automated methods to robustly and scalably collect these data. The Open Datasets Initiative coordinates the collection, funding, and sharing of the resulting publicly-accessible datasets.

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Ideation and Convergence

Participants formed several breakout groups to brainstorm impactful ideas for microbial datasets. As conversations progressed, all groups converged on measuring growth as the optimal starting point.

For the remainder of the workshop, the groups focused their efforts on exploring and refining predictive models and methodologies to gather growth data.

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Possible dataset 1: Growth data relating microbial genomes to cultivation conditions

Figure 1: Dataset 1 Relational Triangle

Prediction tasks:

Participants converged upon this dataset because it could back a wide variety of prediction tasks including:

- *Predict the growth of a microbe in a given environment.*
 - Input: Microbial genome and media formulation.
 - Output: Predicted growth.
- *Optimize media formulation for a specific microbe.*
 - Input: Microbial genome.
 - Output: Media formulation.
- *Design a microbial genome to process a specific feedstock.*
 - Input: Media formulation and desired growth rate.
 - Output: Mesigned microbial genome.

Objective:

- Understand how different environmental conditions interplay with genetics to affect microbe phenotypes (ex: growth and function)
- Understand and predict gene function of a microbe

Experimental Design:

This dataset involves growing 1000 culturable microbes in 1000 cultivation conditions resulting in one million unique experiments. Microbes in this context are defined as unique

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species' genomes and variants thereof spanning bacterial, fungal, and archaeal taxonomy. Growth curves will be measured for each experiment. A suite of additional assay could be considered depending upon feasibility in high-throughput including, RNA-seq, metabolomics, respiration measurements, UV-Vis Spectroscopy, Microscopy, Biofilm assays, and pH measurements.

The genomes of interest are *E. coli* (internal standard), Bacilli, *Vibro natrigens*, and *Pseudomonas putida* as well as industrially-relevant microbes with a focus on biomanufacturing, agriculture, and food/health applications. The use of fungal strains was also discussed, and will be considered for inclusion.

The preliminary conditions of interest agreed upon in the workshop are listed below. The strategy for condition variation will include a human-guided screen for the first ~200 cultivation conditions (Stage 1) followed by an AI-guided condition variation for ~800 cultivation conditions (Stage 2).

- Environmental conditions (Tier 1)
 - Shaking
 - Temp
- Media conditions (Tier 2)
 - Salinity
 - Carbon source
- Media Conditions (Tier 3)
 - pH
 - O₂
 - Nitrogen
 - Metals
 - Antibiotics
 - Vitamin cofactors
 - Light
 - Rich media

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Possible dataset 2: Understanding how to predict microbial community function(s) from metagenomics

Prediction Tasks:

This dataset will support the following prediction tasks:

- *Predict the ecological functions of microbial communities from the metagenome.*
 - Input: Microbial metagenome.
 - Output: Predicted function.
- *Predict the growth of a microbial community in a given environment.*
 - Input: Metagenomic sequence and media formulation.
 - Output: Predicted Growth

Objective:

- Understanding and predicting genetic functions of a microbial community
- Understanding what secondary metabolites are produced during growth of organisms in a community, and how this affects growth and function of the community
- Understanding how different environmental conditions interplay with genetics and secondary metabolites to affect growth and function of a microbe
- Doing experiments of increasing factorial complexity to understand how community function changes with the presence of different microbes, gene perturbations, secondary metabolite creation, and environmental modifications

Experimental Design:

This dataset involves testing community samples and screening for growth under various conditions, with a preliminary focus on growth in the presence of different carbon sources. Samples will be collected from three diverse communities with emphasis on sample homogenization, replicate measurement, and testing at various dilution factors. Natural microbial communities involved in mining (“Metals”) were identified as a specific area of interest. Measurements will include OD, 16S rRNA sequencing, colorimetric methods, microscopy, and total cell area.

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Next Steps

Following the workshop discussions, the next steps involve forming a working group to shepherd the generated ideas into actionable proposals. In the coming months, this group will collaborate to refine and develop the proposal further, implement stage-gates, and ensure they are comprehensive and feasible.

Once the proposals are developed, they will undergo peer review by experts not involved in their development to strengthen ideas. Simultaneously, we will identify partner laboratories and sample providers to collaborate with on data collection, with methods development to begin later this year.

Join the microbes working group!

If you are interested in contributing to this dataset, email us at datasets@alignbio.org or sign up to become a scientific advisor by filling out [this form](#).

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Participants

We express our gratitude to all attendees for their invaluable contributions to the Microbes Ideation Workshop.

Name	Current Affiliation	Bio
Erika DeBenedictis	Align to Innovate	I use automation and directed evolution to understand and engineer proteins. I also founded Align to Innovate and the Open Datasets Initiative out of frustration with how hard it is to get good data in life science!
Pete Kelly	Align to Innovate	At Align, I work at the intersection of Biology and Automation to create a new mechanisms for funding, collecting, and sharing large high-fidelity datasets in the life sciences.
Shantal Al Habib	Align to Innovate	I am a Project Manager on The Open Datasets Initiative team bringing valuable datasets to the scientific community.
Dana Cortade	Align to Innovate	I coordinate community-driven scientific initiatives as Technical Project Manager for Align to Innovate.
Kasia Baranowski	Align to Innovate	I'm a microbiologist/synthetic biologist that was inspired to become a project manager after experiencing its benefits on a strain engineering project. I am now part of the Open Datasets team and I'm here to help make dream datasets a reality!
Carrie Cizauskas	Align to Innovate	I am a veterinarian and wildlife disease ecologist who has been working in biotech for many years as a specialist in collaborations, publications, and scientific communication strategy.

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Lauren Fitch	ArkeaBio	I'm using comparative genomics to identify candidates for a vaccine targeting methanogenic archaea in the cattle rumen.
Rachel Dutton	Astera Institute	My research has focused on identifying the genetic basis of microbial community interactions using in vitro model communities.
Jonathan Jacobs	ATCC	I lead a genomics and bioinformatics team that is producing fully authenticated genomics reference data for ATCC's entire collection of biological materials.
Jon Calles	bnext	I build synthetic cells, abiotic mimics of natural cells and organelles that composed of individually purified biomolecules encapsulated in phospholipid membranes
Henry Lee	Cultivarium	I build tools to study and engineer non-model microbes by combining my background in electrical engineering and signal processing to 20 years of molecular biology and genetics.
Tae Seok Moon	Engineering Biology Research Consortium	I aim to solve global agricultural, environmental, manufacturing, and health problems through engineering biology or systems and synthetic biology.
Adam Winnifrith	Francis Crick Institute/University of Oxford	I study the evolution of proteins and microbes using automation and machine learning.
Elisha Wood-Charlson	Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory	I support a free, open source systems biology data analysis platform that aims to democratize access to microbiome data science, while ensuring credit is given to data contributors/data producers.

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Scott Baker	Pacific Northwest National Laboratory	My research is focused on fungal biotechnology as well as the development of high throughput microbial phenotyping platforms.
Howard Salis	Penn State University	We engineer genetic systems for sensing, computing, and bioconversion by developing and validating predictive models (biophysics + ML) and automated design algorithms. We carry out massively parallel design-build-test-learn cycles utilizing designed oligopools & HT assays. We develop and maintain a popular web-based platform that enables rational design of genetic systems.
Sam Curtis	Rosetta Commons	I study the benefit and risk profiles of biomolecular design software, and how advancements in foundation models affect that calculus.
Patty Rohs	Self	I love microbes- my work has included leading the strain development department at a climate tech company, studying host-microbe interactions, and studying peptidoglycan biosynthesis.
Ivana Cvijovic	Stanford University	I study how evolutionary dynamics shape large populations and constrain what can happen in evolution.
Jacob West-Roberts	Tatta Bio	I study metagenomics-derived sequences, with a focus on genome-resolved methods, taxonomy/phylogeny, and functional annotation techniques.
Rasmus J.N. Frandsen	Technical University of Denmark	I study the evolution and genetic basis for secondary metabolism in filamentous fungi and how we can identify and create new bioactive compounds via genomics, genetic engineering and high-throughput

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		automated phenotyping.
Sasha Milshteyn	Transition Biomining Inc.	I am a generalist with a PhD in biophysics and deep experience with soil metagenomics, currently working on a startup looking to exploit the native microbiome to increase efficiency of acid leach mining of copper.
Satnam Surae	Twig Bio	I lead tech (comp bio, data science, AI/ML and software engineering) at twig bio, a sustainability focussed synthetic biology company that leverages AI to engineer bacteria to produce ingredients and chemicals.
Monica Cesinger	University of California Berkeley	I study methanol-utilizing bacteria to develop sustainable biotechnologies for rare earth element sequestration.
Adrienne Hoarfrost	University of Georgia	I work on AI approaches in environmental microbiology to better understand microbes in the marine environment, their impact on the marine carbon cycle and climate, and their functional potential for basic and translational science.
Paul Jensen	University of Michigan	I combine robotics and AI to build autonomous laboratories for high-throughput microbial phenotyping.
Radhakrishnan Mahadevan	University of Toronto	Our group works on developing models of microbial metabolism and methods for engineering them.

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